

absorbance was same when the complex was boiled for 5–7 min. The complex was not extractable into benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, toluene, and hexane but could be extracted with n-butyl acetate, amyl acetate, diethyl ether, butan-2-one, ethyl acetate, acetyl acetate, isobutanol and methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK). Maximum absorbance was observed with MIBK and hence it was used in this method. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for 30 min.

Under optimum conditions described above, a calibration curve was constructed at 670 nm, and Beer's law being obeyed in the concentration range 25.0–700 μg per 5 ml of the final solution. The Sandell's sensitivity was calculated to be 1.25 μg cm^{-2} at 670 nm (for an absorbance of 0.001) and aliquot containing 500 μg of nabam gave mean absorption of 0.40 with a relative standard deviation of 0.0025.

Composition of the Mo–nabam complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation, and was found to be 2 : 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Sample solutions containing 250 μg of nabam and various amounts of different alkali metal salts or metal ions were prepared and the determination of nabam was studied and the general procedure was applied. The following foreign ions (μg , amounts in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of nabam 250 μg in 5 ml of the final solution: Pb^{2+} (510), Zn^{2+} (66), Bi^{3+} (20), Cd^{2+} (42), Fe^{2+} (10) and Mn^{2+} (10). Cu^{2+} interfered strongly.

Potassium bromide (25 mg), sodium acetate (25 mg), sodium citrate (12 mg), potassium iodide (1 mg), sodium potassium tartrate (10 mg), potassium oxalate (180 μg), ammonium thiocyanate (150 μg) and ethylene diamine (12 mg) were tolerated. EDTA, potassium chloride, potassium nitrate and sodium thiosulphate interfered strongly.

Interference of some of the common reagents like ziram, ferbam, thiram, zineb and maneb which are mostly used as pesticides has been studied. Ziram, ferbam and thiram if present with nabam can be removed by extraction with chloroform. Nabam remaining in the aqueous phase can be determined by the general procedure. Zineb and maneb if present with nabam can be easily separated by extraction with acetonitrile.

Simultaneous determination of nabam and ziram (zinc dimethyl dithiocarbamate) were carried out. Synthetic mixtures of nabam and ziram in various proportions were prepared. Taking advantage of the solubility difference and the colour of the Mo–nabam (blue) and Mo–ziram (yellow), nabam and ziram can be determined simultaneously. Binary mixture was dissolved in 0.1 N NaOH solution. To this solution was added appropriate amount of H_2SO_4 acid and sodium molybdate. Yellow coloured complex formed by ziram with molyb-

denum in cold was extractable into MIBK, whereas blue coloured complex of nabam–Mo was not extractable in cold. Hence, aqueous phase was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and extracted with MIBK. The absorbance of the extracts were measured at 420 nm for ziram–Mo complex and at 670 nm for nabam–Mo complex and the amount of ziram and nabam was determined from the respective calibration curves. Similarly, simultaneous determinations of nabam and thiram, and nabam and ferbam were possible.

Applications: The wide applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples containing nabam upto 500 μg in the aliquot. The method is quite selective for nabam determination in the presence of zineb, maneb, ziram, thiram and ferbam. The proposed method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 15 min for nabam determination after preparation of nabam solution. Binary mixtures of nabam and ziram, nabam and thiram, and nabam and ferbam can be determined simultaneously. It is one of the sensitive methods available for nabam determination and could be used in the analysis of commercial samples.

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Synthetic and Analytical Studies on Pearl 'Bhasma'

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PEARL 'bhasma' is a product used in Indian System of Medicine (Ayurveda) obtained through specialised heat treatment of pearls¹. The reported analysis of this 'bhasma' mentions the presence of only calcium and carbonate^{2,3}. In view of scanty information regarding the constituents of this product, it was considered worthwhile to analyse the pearl-bhasma by modern techniques.

Experimental

Excelar grade chemicals were used. Double-distilled deionised water was used for preparing solutions.

The atomic absorption spectra were recorded on a Varian AA-6 spectrometer, the ir spectra (KBr)

on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, and the FT-ir spectra on a Polytec FIR 30 spectrophotometer. Absorbance measurements were carried out on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer using optically matched quartz cells of 10 mm path length and X-ray powder diffraction spectra on a Philips PW 1700 instrument. A Elico digital flame photometer was used for the estimation of Na and K.

Preparation of 'bhasma': Japanese natural pearls were cleaned and broken into small pieces, tied in a cotton cloth bag and hung in 25% citric acid solution and boiled for 3 h maintaining the same level of solution in the beaker. After cooling, the pearl pieces were washed with warm water.

The purified pearl was triturated with rose water and dried. The dried cakes were kept in an earthen vessel, sealed and gradually heated in a muffle furnace to 950° for 30 min and the heat-treatment was repeated three times. After cooling, the vessel was opened and the material powdered to 200 mesh.

Results and Discussion

The constituents of pearls and its 'bhasma' were estimated quantitatively. Mg, Sr, Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Mn, Mo, Sn and Co were estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. Ca and Mg were estimated complexometrically using calcon and eriochrome black-T as indicators. Sr was estimated gravimetrically as strontium sulphate and Fe spectrophotometrically using thioglycolic acid. Carbonate was estimated by liberating carbon dioxide using Schroedter's apparatus. Carbonate present was also calculated from the quantity of carbon estimated using a Coleman carbon-hydrogen analyser. Na and K were estimated by flame photometer. Average of four analytical results of quantitative estimations are as follows: *Pearl*: Ca, 32.58; Mg, 0.03; Sr, 0.11; Fe, 0.27; Zn, 0.002; Cu, 0.0132; Pb, 0.000001; Na, 0.58; K, 0.01; Mn, 0.025; Mo, <0.05; Sn, 0.03; Co, <0.01; carbonate, 56.4761%; *Pearl 'bhasma'*: Ca, 35.21; Mg, 0.11; Sr, 0.13; Fe, 0.0; Zn, 0.008; Cu, 0.0136; Pb, 0.000001; Na, 0.60; K, 0.01; Mn, 0.0294; Mo, <0.05; Sn, 0.03; Co, <0.01; carbonate, 42.5684%.

Ir spectra: Spectral studies were carried out in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} and also in the region 450-50 cm^{-1} using FT far-ir system. In the pearl spectra two peaks at 110 and 415 cm^{-1} and one band at 330-205 cm^{-1} and in the 'bhasma' spectra

three peaks at 110, 225 and 325 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of calcite⁵. A band at 330-205 cm^{-1} in the pearl spectra and a peak at 225 cm^{-1} in the 'bhasma' spectra indicate presence of SrO_2 . A band at 415 cm^{-1} in the pearl spectra and at 325 cm^{-1} in the 'bhasma' spectra indicate the presence of Fe_2O_3 . A broad band at 3600-3400 cm^{-1} in the pearl spectra indicates MgO with bonded or unbonded OH. A small peak at 3690 cm^{-1} in the 'bhasma' spectra indicates MgO⁶. The peak at 1090 cm^{-1} and a broad band at 1550-1450 cm^{-1} in the pearl spectra indicate CO_3^{2-} but this peak was not observed in the 'bhasma' spectra and the band also shifted slightly⁶. In the pearl spectra four peaks at 725, 875, 1810 and 2540 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of CaCO_3 . In the 'bhasma' spectra three of these peaks are absent and one shifted to 890 cm^{-1} suggesting partial decomposition of CaCO_3 during heat-treatment.

XRPD studies: The inter-planar spacing and relative intensities were calculated. In the raw material, *d* values 3.39, 2.69 and 1.74 indicate aragonite pattern. However, in the 'bhasma' three strong peaks for *d* values 3.03, 2.28 and 1.92 indicate calcite pattern. MgO, SrCO_3 , SrO_2 , Fe_2O_3 and ZnO are indicated in pearl and its 'bhasma' but SrCO_3 is not indicated in the 'bhasma'. Ca(OH)_2 is indicated only in the 'bhasma'^{7,8}

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